

Ancient and modern cities in the work of Constantinos Doxiadis

For a long period, from the Thirties to the Seventies, Constantinos Doxiadis (1913-1975) played a significant role - on a global level, what is more - in the theoretical approach to, and implementation of, the modern city. His oeuvre is certainly enormous, and in its day it achieved striking recognition, though it was also called into question, particularly in Greece, where Doxiadis undertook numerous initiatives and public responsibilities at difficult times. In this short paper, allow me to state from the outset that I shall be selective. I shall deal only with the manner in which his view of the architectural and urban past of ancient Greece - a view which was analytical and only partly historical - converged on the urban thinking of the great Moderns of the inter-War period and the first post-War decades. That encounter revolved around the prospect of formulating the principles of contemporary urbanism as they were applied in theory and practice and as they were projected on to the city of the future. Where theory is concerned, I shall be focusing my attention on Doxiadis' doctoral thesis, published in German in 1937 under the title *Raumordnung im griechische Städtebau*¹ ('Spatial organisation in the building of the Greek cities'), and on an article published first in Greek and, in a longer form, in English in 1964 under the title 'The ancient Greek city and the city of the present'.² The article heralded the publication of a major series of studies of the Ancient Greek Cities, prepared, under Doxiadis' guidance, in the late Sixties and early Seventies by the Athens Centre of Ekistics.³ Following on closely from the large gap between 1937 and 1964 (during which Doxiadis had clearly come an equally long

way), I shall refer to his constructed oeuvre using as examples two projects which appear at first sight to be alien to one another in terms both of location and scale but which, I believe, are very similar: Islamabad, the new capital of Pakistan (1960), which sums up Doxiadis' critique of Chandigarh and Brasilia while at the same time elaborating a direct analogy to ancient Athens and ancient Priene, and the much smaller industrial town of Aspra Spitia (1961), Doxiadis' most important project in Greece in terms of planning and architecture, constructed at Antikyra, not far from ancient Delphi.⁴

Doxiadis' doctoral thesis is a book full of plans, photographs and perspective drawings of ancient Greek cities - dating from the seventh to the first century BC - on which the commentary is a comparatively scanty text. Although Doxiadis was closely associated with archaeologists when the thesis was being written in Berlin, it is neither an archaeological treatise nor a history book. Its author's interests were wholly contemporary, focusing on the search for principles by which space, in its entirety, could be regulated by means of the comparative and experimental testing of hypotheses for which no real documentation was available. His starting-point was the problematic present, for the treatment of which the ancient Greek city was called upon to provide the means. The line of argument is perfectly clear, and is stated at the beginning of the foreword to the thesis: over the past three decades (that is, the three first decades of the twentieth century), a radical change had come about in the conditions prevailing in cities during the previous three millennia. To Doxiadis' mind, there were two reasons for this: the new building materials which had radically altered the scale and form of buildings, and the mechanisation of travel, which had radically altered the scale and form of cities.⁵ These two issues - new materials and the new construction methods that followed from them, and the predominance of the machine - also happened to be arguments of central importance for Modern architecture, and to form the foundations on which the theoretical principles of modern urbanism were stated. Those principles were formulated at the 4th CIAM, a *Congrès* which reached its climax in Athens in 1933, on the premises of the School of Architecture when Doxiadis was still a student there,⁶ and provided Le Corbusier with the platform for his *Charter of Athens*.⁷

The 4th CIAM concept of the contemporary functional city never faded from Doxiadis' mind. Indeed, we could hypothesise that it lay behind his obvious interest in the organisation of the ideal ancient Greek city, an interest which led him, immediately afterwards, to the subject of his doctoral thesis. As he makes clear in the foreword to that thesis, the change in the

conditions of construction and travel (which Doxiadis often appeared to associated less with the optimistic resolution of problems than with their pessimistic accumulation) directed him towards a search for, on the one hand, human scale and, on the other, the secret behind the way in which the ancient Greeks had organised space so as both to gratify human beings and uplift their souls. Using comparative typologies and mathematics - both highly topical at the time in any attempt to interpret good architectural solutions - he studied the sanctuaries and markets of cities in order to discover the principles of a system for arranging buildings in space based on the principles of human knowledge. Doxiadis was convinced that such a system existed and, furthermore, that it was a general theory of organising space, a *theory of urbanism*,⁸ whose rules were of direct significance for the present since «the ancient Greeks designed not isolated objects, as we see being done today, but the parts of a dynamic urban environment».⁹ He went further in explaining his views, saying that as entities the ancient Greek cities were subject to the conditions of development and change current at the time and were not designed to comply with the aesthetic views of an isolated individual about an ideal city which bore no relation to its actual place and time. Indirectly, this was criticism of some of the more messianic approaches of Modernism, and particularly of Le Corbusier (the *ville contemporaine*). For Doxiadis, the decisive factor in planning was the human viewpoint: more specifically, the angle of vision of a human being walking through a city and sensing or perceiving it through the sequence of the organised revelation of its urban entities - of a person turning a street corner, passing through a gateway, or entering a square: the key points on the progression. The aesthetics of the city is not a static matter, but is connected with motion.

Doxiadis' studies of the plans of the ancient Greek cities are generally well enough known, and that of the Acropolis of Athens is particularly familiar. I am not concerned here with the archaeological or architectural precision of that study. I am interested, rather, in seeing it as part of a wider and absolutely contemporary approach which, allusively, contrasts itself to the thinking of Le Corbusier, redefining the artistic terms of the urbanism of someone like Camillo Sitte¹⁰ - the man, indeed, who Le Corbusier had mockingly accused of having got no further than the road of the donkeys.¹¹ Doxiadis, however, was opposed to the mechanical road, to the motor road, and persevered with the perceptive power of the eye of a human being moving across the ground no faster than his two feet could carry him.

The foundations of Doxiadis' thought are only very faintly visible on the surface of the pages of his thesis.

He can be assumed to have been aware of the geometrical interpretations of the visual organisation of the Acropolis, as stated by Auguste Choisy,¹² which were taught in Athens, but what is of particular interest in his case is the fact that he articulates the organisation of space in the city around the revolving eye of a moving person, which resembles a revolving camera located at different points in the space and describing full circles of 360° with ten or twelve present stops in each instance.¹³ The succession of these points, as a sequence of angles of vision during the continuous movement of the human being in space, converges on the rationale of the cinematic way of seeing and organising the same space. It is indeed no coincidence that, at about the same period, Sergei Eisenstein was also addressing himself to the same sources - Choisy and the Acropolis - in order to construct an aesthetic theory of cinema montage, with direct references to human movement and the revolving angle of vision in architectural and urban space.¹⁴

Almost thirty years later, the situation was very different. The modern city had changed radically, and contemporary urbanism had moved from conquest to a position in which it was being subjected to a first wave of harsh criticism. In international thinking, even so, the two large capitals - Brasilia and Chandigarh - had prevailed as original and ideal applications of the principles of Modernism. By this time, the Doxiadis Associates had developed, on the global scene, a type of urban design suitable for human facilities of all kinds on a scale which reminds us of the breadth and ease of the urban design of Le Corbusier as a model which could be repeated. It was the same spirit as that which we encounter later - and my reference is far from coincidental - in the successive 'counterprojects' of Léon Krier.

The arguments of 'The Ancient Greek City and the City of the Present' sum up all the progress which Doxiadis had made from 1937 to 1964 in a direction which, on the one hand, presaged the harsh urban questioning of the 'Moderns' by the 'post-Moderns' (to take its final form ten to fifteen years later) and, on the other, prefigured the rationale of the global village. However self-evident or at any rate inevitable that rationale may seem to us today, then, with the development of the media of communication in an embryonic state, it was still primarily a critique of the metropolitan urbanism of Modernism. The conclusion is stated clearly on the very first page of the text:

"The time has come to turn back to the things of the past so as to see what we can learn from them, as a parallel to our turn to the future which will allow us to see the course we ought to be following. This is a blend of the old things which deserve to survive with the new things which have to be

secured. Such a comparative study leads to the following conclusions:

- a) *The ancient Greek city was built on human dimensions which gave it a human scale and unity.*
- b) *The city of the present has lost its human dimensions.*
- c) *There is an imperative need for human dimensions in the city of the present.*
- d) *The city of to-day also needs other dimensions suitable for the machine and, accordingly, a synthesis of two scales is required: the human scale and the scale of the machine.*
- e) *It is therefore absolutely necessary that we give back to the city its human dimensions, even though we have imposed on it the dimensions of the machine. It was a mistake to let the historic continuity of the human dimensions in the city be lost. We must establish it again, in harmony with the evolution imposed on us by the new factors.*"¹⁵

The conclusion is documented by means of comparative and typological analysis, on the same scale, of the fabric of cities selected from all the periods of history, with Brasilia and Chandigarh as the culminating examples. Emphasis is placed on the correct - that is, human - scale of the city, whose centre can be reached on foot from its periphery in ten minutes, which has streets, squares, blocks and a central public space analogous to the ancient agora.¹⁶ Ancient Athens was without doubt Doxiadis' starting-point, but Priene played an almost equivalent part in his comparative approach, serving as a model for the contemporary urban situation.¹⁷ Of course, Doxiadis was unable to ignore the motor car and rapid travel, but he dealt with it by proposing that human movement be split between that taking place on foot and that involving vehicles. Comparing ancient Priene with the contemporary megalopolis, he put forward the idea of an articulated and perpetually evolving city, one which would overcome all the defects of modern urbanism. In other words, his proposal was for a network of small cities, on the scale of Priene and in accordance with its rationale, to be located in the interstices of a network for the circulation of mechanical media - that is, motor vehicles. Islamabad is the ideal example of the model: small communities of the Priene type, with populations of 1,000 families or 5,000 people, are juxtaposed as the members of a potentially global network each of whose units is in the simultaneous service of the part and the whole.¹⁸ Doxiadis summed up the idea in his comparison of the ancient Greek city and Islamabad:

"We cannot build new cities under the influence only of the model of the ancient Greek city, since

*in that way we will never solve the problems of the modern era. However, we have to create cities which consist of elements based on the human scale. Human communities of the first to the fifth degree are such elements: we can combine them correctly and repeat them as many times as is necessary to make the contemporary city. The modern city should be a synthesis of the human scale and the mechanical scale. Smaller units, which can be planned on human dimensions, should be based on the human scale, while larger areas are based on the mechanical one. Only in this way will we be serving humankind while at the same time improving the performance of the machine, exhausting its potential."*¹⁹

The idea is even better expressed at the end of the English version of the same article, where the path towards the terminology of the *ecumenopolis* - or to use the current phrase, the *global village* - is opened up:

*"When man succeeds in mastering these large dimensions, the whole world will be one city. When space satellites allow him to survey the entire globe and television enables him to hear the news from every corner of the world, the mechanical dimensions of the city will shrink to those of an ancient Greek city. Man will not only live in a small human community and dominate it by human dimensions, he will also live in a world-wide community, which he will dominate by means of the mechanical dimensions which he has created. We are undoubtedly moving towards ecumenopolis, a world city. (...) Our environment will become less and less human, and in order to function, the city will have to rely, to an increasing extent, on machines. (...) When this materializes, unless we have taken steps to make this city a human one, the end of our civilization will be near. (...) In the interests of man, we should return to our ancient heritage and see how the ancient Greek city can be of special help to us."*²⁰

One might stop there, at the formulation of this overall urban model, addressed to Islamabad and thus to every other city in the world and so to Greece, proposing the continuous proliferation of the ideal model of Priene projected on to the global communications network. However, there are reasons why the centripetal and holistic organisation of urban space, the rejection of Brasilia and Chandigarh as evolutionary results of the Charter of Athens, is of particular interest to us in Greece; those reasons are bound up with the new town for 5,000 people which the Doxiadis Associates designed to house

the staff of the Pechiney aluminium plant and is known by the name of Aspra Spitia (literally, 'white houses').²¹

At first sight, the town is a simple and isolated community, a unit based on a more general model, a contemporary Priene. It has every amenity imaginable,²² and it could have been a self-contained node on the global network of ecumenopolis. The interest here, however, lies in the fact that the general urban scale descends an entire step in the direction of architecture, conveying an idea, from a different angle, of the mild questioning of Modernism. Let us examine the basic arguments which conscientiously differentiate Aspra Spitia from the Modern idea, from the aesthetics and internationalism of the industrial city, in the direction of a Greek community equipped with all the characteristics of local societies.

"It didn't take (...) long to reject the idea of a typical industrial settlement with uniform apartment buildings where the people would feel like expatriates and refugees and where living would be but a continuation of working in the mechanized environment of the new factory. On the contrary, they decided that they should create a 'Greek city' in which people could easily identify all the cultural traditions they were brought up with and could preserve them as a most valuable inheritance."²³
"The conclusion drawn (...) was that they needed a simple, clear and forceful plan that could provide room for these qualities with its 'invisible geometry' holding the varied parts together; that they needed a simple, strong and 'primitive' architecture composed of natural, local materials, which the people could improve upon by adding their flower pots and pergolas, rather than a modern architecture in which visual equilibrium can be upset by the addition of a dot."²⁴

"Exterior finish materials of the houses are stone, concrete and wood joinery. The great majority of the stone walls of the houses are whitewashed except for a small number, in special locations, where a special accent was sought by leaving the stone unpainted or by the use of color. By eliminating the 'accident' of color, the whitewashing of the walls gives the houses greater sculptural clarity and simplicity, accentuates their texture and gives a marvelously 'Greek' effect combined with the color and shape of the olive trees."²⁵

"This small settlement possesses the special urban feeling characteristic of Greek cities of the past - a feeling induced by a town in which cohesion does not abolish individuality, privacy in interior yards does not conflict with social togetherness in the street or square and the physical scale and

treatment express the hierarchy of values in city living."²⁶

Aspra Spitia is not simply a town for workers living in better or worse conditions and experiencing better or worse social relations at work: that would certainly be quite a different debate. Aspra Spitia is the paradigmatic implementation of the unit of the contemporary city which Doxiadis had been seeking from the Thirties to the Sixties and Seventies. It is the Priene of contemporary Greece, and a kind of synopsis of the primacy of Doxiadis' Greek model in global urbanism and architecture. At the same time, it is the built implementation of a critical development of the principles of the functional city laid down by the 4th CIAM and the Charter of Athens, which Doxiadis had been promoting at precisely the same period.

What else could have been the meaning of a floating Symposium - not simply a Congrès - held in July 1963, exactly thirty years on from July 1933, on a vessel now named *Nea Hellas* ('New Greece') voyaging among the Greek islands, with Sigfried Giedion, secretary to the CIAMs of former times, as keynote speaker, ending, symbolically, at the ancient Greek city of Delos, now uninhabited, in a clear reference to the Delian Festival, and culminating in the ambitious *Declaration of Delos*, symbolically named from the island and intended to become a Charter?²⁷ The failure of the existing cities was once more the starting-point, although now that included the implementation of the functional city envisaged by the 4th CIAM. The redemptive city of the future was to be a modernised projection of the ideal ancient Greek city of Doxiadis' vision, in which the human and the mechanical scales were combined. To this end, and in order to lay claim simultaneously to the global quality of a contemporary rationale and the singularity of the local community and aesthetics, Doxiadis had quite appropriately turned to collaboration with 'regional' architects such as Hassan Fathy (1956-1961)²⁸ and had equally appropriately invited Marshall McLuhan, whose *Understanding Media* had appeared the year before,²⁹ to attend the Delos Symposium.

As a reply to Chandigarh and Brasilia, Islamabad is in architectural and urban terms the general application of an overall rule whose sole European implementation was Aspra Spitia. The comparison is inevitable between these two projects and the original *Unité d'Habitation* in Marseilles, the vertically-arranged autonomous community whose repetitions were to add up to the radiant new city of Le Corbusier. The most essential difference was that Doxiadis' equally autonomous community developed horizontally, as if the multi-storey city had become recumbent and as a rejection of any advanced

constructional technology or mechanical equipment. It is a notional aesthetic continuity of the human being still walking through the local tradition, though capable simultaneously of being omnipresent.

Dimitris Philippides, one of the very few scholars to have written of the almost unknown Aspra Spitia project, was thus quite right to note, from his own quite different angle of vision, that "here, the references to 'Greekness' are deliberate". In a footnote, he added that "although Aspra Spitia is rather indistinctly reminiscent of a village, it is much more reminiscent of the ekistic projects of the Doxiadis Associates for other countries".³⁰ However, "international urban practice" was once more not the "ancestor" of the project, as Philippides goes on to note, but simply a fellow-traveller, or the other side of the same coin. Indeed, the essence of the architecture of Islamabad is just as Greek, just as regional, just as human and at the same time just as ecumenical as that of Aspra Spitia. In other words, the gap between Chandigarh and Islamabad is just as small (in geographical, cultural, chronological, urban and perhaps architectural terms) as the gap between Le Corbusier and Doxiadis - though the gap between both of them and the capitals they envisaged may remain for ever unbridgable.

NOTES

¹ K.A. Doxiadis, *Raumordnung im griechischen Städtebau*, Heidelberg, Kurt Vowinkel Verlag, 1937; *Architectural Space in Ancient Greece*, trans. Jacqueline Tyrwhitt, Cambridge Mass., MIT Press, 1972. This translation was preceded by an abridged but concise publication in English to which Doxiadis often referred: 'The Greek City Plan', *Landscape* 6, no 1, Autumn 1956, pp. 19-26. The basic principles of the thesis had already been published in Greek by Dimitris Pikionis ('Η Θεωρία του αρχιτέκτονος Κ.Α. Δοξιάδη για την διαμόρφωση του χώρου εις την αρχαία αρχιτεκτονική', *To Trito Mati*, nos. 7-12, 1937, pp. 234-246), and this publication had signalled the beginning of a seminal controversy between Pikionis and Panayotis Michelis. This is a fascinating topic, since Pikionis had helped Doxiadis in the early period of his studies and later applied the spirit of his proportions to projects such as the landscaping of Athens Acropolis and the Xenia Hotel at Delphi. I hope to return to the subject in another paper.

² K.A. Doxiadis, 'Η αρχαία ελληνική και η σημερινή πόλη', *Architektoniki*, 46, July-August 1964, pp. 46-59; K.A. Doxiadis, 'The ancient Greek city and the city of the present', *Ekistics*, 18, no 108, November 1964, pp. 346-364. Both articles were variations on an address delivered by Doxiadis to the 6th International Congress of the European Cultural Foundation, held in Athens in May 1964 and accompanied by an exhibition of his drawings organised by the Athens Institute of Technology. Only a few copies were made of the duplicated Greek text of the speech (pp. 18), and it is now in the Doxiadis Archive. Doxiadis himself later referred to a third and final version, 'The Ancient Greek City and the City of the Present', in *The Living Heritage of Greek*

Antiquity, European Cultural Foundation, The Hague, Mouton, 1967, pp. 192-211.

³ The series of studies began in 1968 and involved the collaboration of many eminent researchers - in the majority, Greek archaeologists - but in Doxiadis' mind these researchers were clearly a continuation of those he had already conducted. The first volume was written by Arnold Toynbee (*An Ekistical Study of the Ancient Greek City-State*, Athens, Athens Centre of Ekistics, 1971), but the true introduction to the series was the second volume: C.A. Doxiadis, *The Method for the Study of the Ancient Greek Settlements*, Athens, Athens Centre of Ekistics, 1972. (For the connections drawn by Doxiadis himself to the publications listed above, cf. pp.x, 1 and p. 39, notes 1 and 2.) A further 22 volumes followed, and 17 studies still remain to be published. A broader review of the project was provided by three annual reports: 'Ancient Greek Settlements', *Ekistics*, January 1971, pp. 4-19; 'Ancient Greek Settlements: Second Annual Report', *Ekistics*, February 1972, pp. 76-89, and 'Ancient Greek Settlements: Third Report', *Ekistics*, January 1973, pp. 7-16.

⁴ This selective approach obviously passes over entire decades and wide aspects of the oeuvre which would certainly be of interest for a different interpretation: one of a more historical or more political nature. I am aware of the leaps, and I take them in the belief that in focusing on a few crucial action plans I will help to restore one of the most important and long-lasting threads running through Doxiadis' thinking - and, needless to say, the thread in which my own researches are most interested.

⁵ Cf. Doxiadis, *Architectural Space in Ancient Greece*, p. ix. I refer to the English version, which is a partial revision of the original book, not only because it is more generally familiar but also because it is more in keeping with the thinking and the projects of the Sixties. Furthermore, the fact that a quasi-archaeological thesis of the late pre-War period should have been translated into English after 35 years - and by Jacqueline Tyrwhitt, at that - is far from irrelevant to the expansion of the second part of Doxiadis' international activities and researches.

⁶ Doxiadis passed the entrance examinations to the School of Architecture of the National Technical University in 1930, and received his degree in 1935.

⁸ *La Charte d'Athènes* (Paris, Plon, 1943), drawn up by Le Corbusier, and the corresponding book by José Luis Sert, *Can Our Cities Survive? An ABC of Urban Problems, Their Analysis, Their Solutions* (1942), are personal versions of the conclusions reached by the 4th CIAM, although to the public mind Le Corbusier's Charter and the Congress conclusions have become more or less synonymous. For the main papers and the conclusions of the Congress, see 'Le IV^e Congrès International d'Architecture Moderne, "La ville fonctionnelle"', *Annales Techniques, Organe Officiel de la Chambre Technique de Grèce*, no. 44-46, 15 October - 15 November 1933, pp. 995-1093 and 1128-1192.

⁸ Cf. Doxiadis, *Architectural Space in Ancient Greece*, p. 3.

⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 4.

¹⁰ Cf. Camillo Sitte, *Der Städtebau nach seinen Künstlerischen Grundsätzen*, Vienna, Verlag von Carl Graeser, 1889. Although Doxiadis does not refer directly to Sitte, who is not cited in the thesis, the more general aesthetic approach to urban space in the German-speaking world was along similar lines (cf. Albert Erich Brinckmann, *Platz und Monument. Untersuchungen zur*

Geschichte und Aesthetik der Stadtbaukunst in neuerer Zeit, Berlin, E. Wasmuth, 1912, and idem, *Stadtbaukunst. Geschichtliche Querschnitte und neuzeitliche Ziele*, Berlin-Neubabelsberg, Athenaion, 1920).

¹¹ Cf. Le Corbusier, *Urbanisme*, Paris, G. Crès, 1925, chap. 1: «Le chemin des ânes. Le chemin des hommes».

¹² Cf. Auguste Choisy, *Histoire de l'architecture*, Paris, Gauthier-Villars, 1899, vol. 1, chap. XI, 'Architecture Greque', section entitled 'Le pittoresque et la symétrie perspective', pp. 409-422, and Pikionis, *op. cit.*, pp. 235-236.

¹³ "Radii from the vantage point -[the first and most important position from which the whole site could be observed]- determined the position of three corners of each important building, so that a three-quarter view of each was visible. (...) The radii that determined the corners of the important buildings formed certain specific angles from the viewpoint, equal in size on each site. These fell into two categories: angles of 30°, 60°, 90°, 120°, and 150°, corresponding to a division of the total field of 360° into twelve parts; and angles of 36°, 72°, 108°, and 144°, which resulted from division of the total field of vision into ten parts." (Doxiadis, *Architectural Space in Ancient Greece*, p. 5)

¹⁴ Cf. Sergei M. Eisenstein, 'Montage and Architecture', with an introduction by Yves-Alain Bois, *Assemblage*, 10, December 1989, pp. 110-131.

15. Doxiadis, 'Η αρχαία ελληνική και η σημερινή πόλη', p. 46.

¹⁶ The whole process contains elements reminiscent of the rather later analysis of Léon Krier, even on the level of the presentation or the horizontal linear scale of 10 minutes' walking. There are further similarities later on, in the articulated city of the communities on the human scale.

¹⁷ We are not unaware of the studies conducted, on Doxiadis' responsibility and probably his initiative, of the organisation of the Greek village at the time when he was Minister of Reconstruction, or the large-scale research project into the organisation of the neighbourhoods of Athens conducted in the early Sixties by the Athens Centre of Ekistics with a multidisciplinary and international team (cf. Suzanne Keller: 'Planning at Two Scales: The Work of C.A. Doxiadis', *Ekistics*, 282, May/June 1982, pp. 172-174). However important these studies may have been for defining the communities of the human scale, Doxiadis never hints at their existence in the texts to which we are referring, obviously because he had chosen to find ideological support for his model in ancient Greece and not the modern country.

¹⁸ The Master Plan for Islamabad was prepared in 1960 and put into effect at once. Cf. K.A. Doxiadis, 'Islamabad, The Creation of a New Capital', *Town Planning Review* 36, no 1, April 1965, pp. 1-28. For a wider bibliography and evaluation of the project, cf. Dusan Botka, 'Islamabad after 33 years', *Ekistics* 373, July/August 1995, pp. 209-235.

¹⁹ Doxiadis, 'Η αρχαία ελληνική και η σημερινή πόλη', p. 47.

²⁰ Doxiadis, 'The ancient Greek city and the city of the present', pp. 363-364.

²¹ The project was commissioned in 1961 and the last house in the original programme was completed in 1965 (cf. *Aspra Spitia: A new 'Greek' city*, a four-page information leaflet produced by Doxiadis Associates, International Consultants on Development and Ekistics, s.a., most of which was also published as an article:

Doxiadis Associates, 'Άσπρα Σπίτια', *Architektoniki*, 53, September-October 1965, pp. 54-57).

²² In 1979, the Athens newspapers were flooded with an advertisement in which a panoramic view of the town was accompanied by the following text:

«Aspra Spitia is a 'village' of 4,500 people, 500 cars, six tennis courts, modern boutiques and an annual festival.

«Aspra Spitia: the standard of living and opportunities of the big city without the crowds, the pollution, the noise and the stress. Imagine a 'village' with its own shopping centre, bank, newspaper, theatre, two cinemas, café, ballet school, foreign language school, and a complete range of educational facilities, all the way from nursery school to tutorial college.

«Imagine a 'village' in which the sports facilities include a football ground with a grass pitch, volleyball, basketball and tennis courts, sailing, a winter sports centre and a modern shooting range.

«Imagine a 'village' designed by Constantinos Doxiadis, by the sea and amid verdant greenery, all of whose residents - scientists, labourers, housewives, parents, sports enthusiasts, chess-players, Scouts, art-lovers - have a chance to play a creative part in social life though their clubs and associations.

«When the people who were going to be working in the aluminium plant first arrived here, from all over Greece, they dreamed of the day they would be going home.

«Today, the first pensioners in the town want to stay on in Aspra Spitia.»

²³ Doxiadis Associates, "Άσπρα Σπίτια," p. 54.

²⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 54.

²⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 57.

²⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁷ For the Symposium, organised by the Athens Institute of Technology from 6 to 13 July, with the participation of 34 eminent speakers from all over the world, and for the *Declaration of Delos*, cf. 'The Delos Symposium', *Ekistics* 16, no 95, October 1963, pp. 203-267. Over the years which followed, a total of twelve Delos Symposia were held.

²⁸ Cf. James Steele, *An Architecture for People: The Complete Works of Hassan Fathy*, London, Thames & Hudson, 1997, pp. 109-123. On the first page of the much later 'Red Book' of C.A. Doxiadis and J.G. Papaioannou, *Ecumenopolis: The Inevitable City of the Future*, Athens, Athens Centre of Ekistics, 1974, Hassan Fathy was acknowledged as a member of the small team of experts who elaborated the central ideal of ecumenopolis - "the team of experts that participated in the intensive early discussions on the project (mainly in 1961 and 1962), that clarified many of its basic issues." (p. ix).

²⁹ Marshall McLuhan, *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man*, New York, McGraw-Hill, 164.

³⁰ Dimitris Philippides, *Νεοελληνική Αρχιτεκτονική*, Athens, Melissa, 1984, p. 334.

Fig. 1 – Athens, Acropolis III, after 450 B.C. Plan. Use of the Twelve- and Ten-Part System. Source: Doxiadis, *Architectural Space in Ancient Greece*, p.37.

Fig. 2 – The Asclepeion at Cos. Plan. Use of the Ten-Part System. Source: Doxiadis, *Architectural Space in Ancient Greece*, p.130.

Fig. 3 – The Agora and the Temple of Zeus at Magnesia, Second Century B.C. Plan. Use of the Ten-Part System. Source: Doxiadis, *Architectural Space in Ancient Greece*, p.157.

Fig. 4-6 – Magnesia, Agora. Perspectives from points A, B and C. Source: Doxiadis, *Architectural Space in Ancient Greece*, p.158-160.

19. Πόλεις διαφόρων εποχών ταξινομημένες χρονικά και γεωγραφικά.
 Cities of various periods classified chronologically and geographically.

20. Πλατείες διαφόρων εποχών.
 Squares of various periods.

Fig. 7 – Cities and squares of various periods classified chronologically and geographically. Πηγή: Δοξιάδης, "Η αρχαία ελληνική και η σημερινή πόλη", p.52.

Fig. 8. – Olynthos. Residential Quarters. Source: Doxiadis, "The Ancient Greek City and the City of the Present", p.356.

Fig. 9 – "Islamabad, an example of synthesis in two scales. Human communities are linked together and are effectively served by the machine."
Source: Δοξιάδης, "Η αρχαία ελληνική και η σημερινή πόλη", p.57.

Ἀθήνα 400 π.Χ

Islamabad – κοινότητα V

Fig. 10 – "Ancient Athens and Priene on the same scale as a 4th and 5th degree community of Islamabad." Source: Δοξιάδης, "Ἡ αρχαία ελληνική και ἡ σημερινή πόλη", p.55.

Fig. 11 – “Views of ancient Priene and of the new capital of Pakistan, Islamabad. A common characteristic, the human scale.” Source: Δοξιάδης, “Η αρχαία ελληνική και η σημερινή πόλη”, p.54.

Fig. 12 – A street and houses in a 5th degree community in Islamabad. Source: Doxiadis archive.

Fig. 13 – Aspra Spitia. General view. Source: Doxiadis Associates, *Aspra Spitia: A new 'Greek' city* [p. 1].

Fig. 14 – Aspra Spitia. Master plan. Source: Doxiadis Associates, *Aspra Spitia: A new 'Greek' city* [p. 2].

Fig. 15 – Aspra Spitia. Typical row of two-storey houses. Elevation. Source: Γραφείο Δοξιάδη, "Άσπρα Σπίτια", p.55.

Fig. 16 – Aspra Spitia. Two-storey houses. Source: Doxiadis Associates, *Aspra Spitia: A new 'Greek' city* [p. 4].

Fig. 17 – Aspra Spitia. Front (detail) of two storey house for upper incomes." Source: Γραφείο Δοξιάδη, "Άσπρα Σπίτια", p. 57.

KEYWORDS

Doxiadis, Constantinos, Greece (ancient), Islamabad,

Panayotis Tournikiotis, born 1955, Athens, Greece. Architect. Assistant professor of Theory at the National Technical University of Athens, School of Architecture. Publications: *Adolf Loos* (New York, 1994); *The Parthenon and its Impact in Modern Times* editor (New York, 1996); *The Historiography of Modern Architecture* (Cambridge, Mass., 1999). Coordinator of the Greek DOCOMOMO Working Party.